
The Web of Clashing Cultural Values: Turkey and the West in Orhan Pamuk's *Snow*

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Abstract

Within the framework of Orhan Pamuk's fiction the shortcomings, failures and idealism of various projects of modernization become prominent and he questions the grand narrative of Eurocentric notions of progress and development. He repeatedly returns to the concerns of the past heritage rather than a continual linear drive towards newness and such a technique enables him to project the tension between pro-Western modernity and tradition in the context of Islamic culture. Turkey's first Nobel laureate, Ferit Orhan Pamuk's first utmost political novel is *Snow*. The protagonist's name is Ka, who is strongly rooted in Western secularism and after arriving in Kars, a peripheral city in turkey, he started to realize that his identity is divided. Through different spatial images the author invokes a very ambiguous urban space which is divided between two extreme groups. The question, if the women of Kars are allowed to wear headscarf or not, raise new notions of space, politics and identity and explore the interface between theories of cultural difference and everyday realities of political practice. The Secular state has banned headscarves and the political Islamists want to inscribe their ideologies over the ban, neglecting the voice of the 'headscarf' girls who at the end resort to suicide. This generates a very practical question about whether the civil rights of particular groups may be sacrificed in order to uphold the rights of others. The 'headscarf' girls willingly opted for self-annihilation as they found the clashing cultural values and the clashing political views traumatic. The author never passes his unequivocal judgemental comments. Rather he presents spatio-temporal descriptions of Kars to Frankfurt and emphasizes the state of being torn between two ideologies. This paper aims to show how the identity of a subject position need to be understood not only historically but also spatially as different local political movements have a crucial role to play in their identity formation. Above all politics is territorial and the territories may be real, imaginary or symbolical.

Keywords

grand narrative, modernity, spatial, cultural memory, geopolitical

Samuel P. Huntington in his book *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of the World Order* (1996), speculated that “the fundamental source of conflict in this new [post-Cold War] world will not be primarily ideological or primarily economic... will be cultural” (22). Countries on the fault lines between two civilizations, he argues—most notably Russia, Mexico and Turkey—are ‘torn countries’ that display “a fair degree of cultural homogeneity but are divided over, whether their society belongs to one civilization or another” (42). The case of Turkey represents in miniature the subterranean conflicts between the forces of Western modernity and traditional religious values. Turkey’s population is mainly Muslim, but at the beginning of the Twentieth century, it underwent a forced Westernization at the hands of its national hero Kemal Ataturk, so much so that he prohibited the teaching of Arabic in schools and replaced the Turkish alphabet by the Latin one. Huntington observes how for several centuries non-Western peoples envied the economic prosperity, technological sophistication, military power and political cohesion of Western societies. He termed it as “Kemalist attitudes” (93), when non-Western elite thinks that to be powerful and rich, they have to become like the West. Orhan Pamuk in the same manner opines in his non-fictional work, *Other Colours* that the Istanbul elites were dazzled by the superiority of the West and the underlying logic of Kemal Ataturk’s westernizing reforms was the conviction that Turkey’s weakness and poverty stem from its tradition (230). Kemalist Secular discourse seems to focus only on the different manifestations of Turkish nationalism and pan-Turkism, if Istanbul lies in the centre of Turkey and thereby regulating the collective ideology of the nation, but peripheral city like Kars have different geographical manifestation. He believes if “a Turkish novelist who failed to imagine the Kurds and other minorities, and who neglected the black spots in his country’s unspoken history, would have in my view, produced something hollow” (228).

Orhan Pamuk is mostly credited as a postmodern author. Most of the prominent critics and reviewers of Orhan Pamuk’s works stress on or try to comprehend his works on the basis of the fact that he is a prominent figure of world literature, ignoring the local cultural background entirely. But when an author’s work has been translated into more than fifty languages and the author is also a Noble Laureate, he is more than a major contributor in the globalized world of modern letters. We can take him as the central figure in any understanding of the “new” Turkey. For Erdag Goknar, Turkey’s most translated novelist, Ferit Orhan Pamuk has developed as a “psycho-historical anthropologist of national culture and identity” through his fictional oeuvre.

Pamuk’s first political novel is *Snow*, originally the title of this novel is *Kar* (Turkish word for snow) and the setting the novel is Kars, a city in north-east Turkey, the province of Kars has peopled and furrowed many incidents which gave birth to the narrative. The name of the place and the protagonist’s name are intertwined thereby suggesting their shared fate of isolation. A terrible blizzard cuts off the city from the rest of the Turkey. During the initial presentation of the narrative the narrator calls the city a ‘shadow world’, and a ‘border city’. The protagonist has returned to Istanbul after twelve years, to attend his mother’s funeral, he is a poet who ‘enjoyed some small, enigmatic fame as Ka in both Turkey and Germany’ (*Snow*, 5). After four days stay in Istanbul Ka has decided to come to Kars, a city with old Russian stone houses, thousand year old Armenian churches, decayed Ottoman buildings, Pasha’s mansions and hamams and Kurdish, Georgian and

Circassian tribes. Through the experiences of Ka from Frankfurt to Kars, his quest for creating and enscripting his poetry, Pamuk succeeds in representing the Turkish crisis where Kars acts as the microcosm of the nation. The Republic of Turkey, after its creation in 1922, has faced military coups in 1960, 1971 and in 1980. Every military coup is followed by political unrest. The military also arrested thousands of people; dozens were executed, while many others were tortured or simply disappeared. In the novel Kars witnesses one such military coup which is staged very tactfully by Sunay Zaim during the live telecast of the play “*My Fatherland or My Headscarf*” in the National Theatre. Z Demirkol, a member of special task force whose goal is to suppress the rise of political Islam and Kurdish separatist guerrillas, and two other men joined him and bolted from the National Theatre, at first the audience take it as a part of Brechtian device but they started firing, killing innocent boys of the city’s religious school and Necip, a boy who wanted to be science fiction writer, is one of them.

There was scattered applause from the back, from people presumably in the habit of clapping at anything—or perhaps they were scared... It was as if they’d decided that the dead bodies before their eyes belonged to the dream world of the stage; ...

“This is not a play; it is the beginning of a revolution,” he said reproachfully.

“We are prepared to go to any lengths to protect our fatherland. Put your faith in the great and honorable Turkish army! ...”. (156)

The military regime, however, had many authoritarian tendencies; they suppressed civic freedom and totally neglected the oppositional tendencies that were particularly visible in rural areas and small towns. In this context of regulating, tormenting and silencing different local movements, Edward Soja’s contention is worthy of quoting. In his book *Postmodern Geographies*, he rightly comments:

To maintain adhesiveness, the civic centre has always served as a key surveillant node of the state, supervising locales of production, consumption and exchange. It still continues to do so, even after centuries of urban recomposition and restructuring, after waves of reagglomerative industrialization. (35)

The novel sets two mutually contradictory ‘worlds’ against each other, where fundamentalists formulate their set of principles depending upon ‘the’ text Quran which is privileged over the spoken words and the radical secularists only rely on the Kemalist Constitution, denying any individual’s voice. Esra Mirze Santesso in her essay “Silence, Secularism, and Fundamentalism in *Snow*” observes:

Thus, Pamuk attempts to blur the lines between religious inflexibility and secular despotism, describing *both* positions as essentially fundamentalist, *both* dedicated to silencing the other. By paying particular attention to various forms of fundamentalism (textual, religious, and secular), Pamuk examines the predicament of subscribing to rigid doctrines that promise stability at the expense of plurality. It is my contention that this politically charged novel is Pamuk’s response to the silences, taboos, and indictments that are the by-products of both religion and nationalism. (128)

Ka, who is strongly rooted in Western secularism, started to realize that his identity is divided. He is from a bourgeois family in cosmopolitan Istanbul; he has been in exile in the West. For the Islamist boys, he is an atheist and a direct embodiment of Europe. The secular Republic also does not want him as he is writing about the suicides. Blue, the underground leader of political Islamists makes fun of Ka's borrowed Western attitudes to prove that Ka is only a mimic man parroting the European notions about freedom, secularism and democracy without knowing his own culture. Ka seems to exemplify the Turkish identity which is torn between the nation's past and the forces of modernity. In *Snow* the protagonist, comes to "a border city" (13), Kars, to write an article about the recent surge of suicides among young Turkish girls protesting the official ban on wearing headscarves. The narrator also names the town as "shadow world". Such epithets stress the 'liminal' identity of the town which once was an important station for trade route, 'being on the border between two defunct empires, the Ottoman and the Russian' (20). Once prosperous, now, the city has plunged into 'destitution, depression and decay' (21).

Through different spatial images the author invokes a very ambiguous urban space which is divided between two extreme groups and the author too maintains silence over which group is right or wrong. The author never passes his unequivocal judgemental comments. Rather he presents spatio-temporal descriptions of Kars to Frankfurt and emphasizes the state of being torn between two ideologies. Ka himself belongs to a secular, republican family and he had no religious tuition. From the very beginning the narrator makes us aware about Ka's Leftist Republican views but after arriving in Kars he realizes that for his poetic inspiration he must be inclined towards the mystical and sacred.

In the novel different characters remind Ka about his Istanbul bourgeoisie origin and calls him an atheist. In Chapter 9 of the novel Fazil and Mesut, teenage boys from religious high school asked Ka if he is an atheist. Mesut believes that believers' and non-believers' cemeteries should be kept separated otherwise "it would bring disquiet to the souls of believers to lie in the same cemeteries with the godless" (87). These Borgesian remarks regarding God's existence emerges from their pure faith but there are characters like Blue, the underground leader of political Islamists who can abuse such pure religiosity. Political Islamists, who seek power by feeding on the fears of religious groups (their slogan: "Give your vote to the Prosperity party, the party of God, we've fallen into this destitution because we've wandered off the path of God" [26]). We cannot ignore how the discourse of nationalism, in its continuous efforts of silencing the believers has made them fanatics. In the early years of the Republic, the Kemalist government made conscious efforts to blur the Ottoman past from the psyche of the Turkish generation. This generates a very practical question about whether the civil rights of particular groups may be sacrificed in order to uphold the rights of others. The 'headscarf' girls willingly opted for self-annihilation as they found the clashing cultural values and the clashing political views traumatic. But in Kars the thing is different with the surge of Political Islam, women from every strata donned their headscarves and the "streets of Kars are filled with women in headscarves of every kind" (21). Muzaffer Bey, the ex-mayor recollects how during the 1940's they had to search the entire city for a black scarf to use in a play. Political Islamists wanted to use the headscarf girls in their battle against Republican Party; they have their own political agenda. Here lies the question if the Islamists are against suicide or not as Koran prohibits

suicide. The question, if the women of Kars are allowed to wear headscarf or not, raise new notions of space, politics and identity and explore the interface between theories of cultural difference and everyday realities of political practice. Other two minor characters also throw some light on the clashing values and they are in the end too unable to find any solution, the fanatic murderer shot in the head and in the chest of the director of the Education Institute. In chapter 5, “The First and Last Conversation between the Murderer and His Victim”, the murderer asserts---“It’s the headscarf that gives women respect and a comfortable place in society. We’ve heard this from so many women who’ve chosen later in life to cover themselves.” (46). The Director of the Education Institute tries a lot to make him understand that when a woman sheds her headscarf, she occupies a more comfortable place in society and she can earn respect from the society. The narrator never intrudes, rather he made the reader visualize the vast arena of Turkey’s political past, the entanglement of two different worldviews and Ka’s existential approach to these worldviews. In order to be the part of ‘world space’ of multi-national capitalism in the form of European Union, the Kemalist ideology of Turkish Republic effaced its Ottoman past. Soja rightly argues, ‘the geography and history of capitalism intersect in a complex social process which creates a constantly evolving historical sequence of spatialities’ (127).

The fabrication of Islamic identities of these headscarf girls started within their families, later the society represses them by continuous masculine regulation. One part of the society demands that Muslim women must maintain a visual contrast to the white Western women but with the surge of Pan-Turkism how could they ignore the Eurocentric domination. Women like Ipek, Hande and Kadife can ignore such flux, they hold their decision upright. Women like Teslime have found suicide to be their only tenable form of resistance in a state system plagued by an anxiety about change and that otherwise ignores their choice. Suicide is their last resort for asserting their choice. In her review, "Headscarves to Die For," of the novel, *Snow*, Margaret Atwood (2004) notes that: “Women have not been notably of central importance in Pamuk's previous novels, but *Snow* is a departure . . . there's a chorus: The headscarf girls. Those scrapping for power on both sides use these dead girls as symbols, having put unbearable pressure on them while they were alive.” Colleen Ann Lutz Clemens observes about the suicide girls, “The women's bodies are the pawns, and they kill themselves in response to this use of their bodies. Both sides inscribe their ideologies on the bodies of the women: That is, they must not or must cover their heads as signs of their secular freedom (the state) or their religious obligation (those who desire a theocratic state), both sides tugging at the women”. In Chapter 43, “Women Commit Suicide to Save Their Pride: The Final Act” where Sunay decided to stage a second play, “A Tragedy in Kars”, inspired by Thomas Kyd’s *The Spanish Tragedy*, he compelled Kadiffe to play the central role who is about to face with “two important decisions—about baring her head and about committing suicide” (403). During the second performance the vague line between performance and reality ends. The violence unleashed during both the performances demonstrates the violent and brutal ambitions of the state surveillance. Kadife bared her and all the citizens of Kars gazed in awe at Kadife’s long, beautiful, brown hair as the cameraman show the courage to put the focus on it but “when he had found the nerve to zoom in on her face, it became clear that Kadife was deeply embarrassed, like a woman whose dress had come undone in a crowded public place” (412). The act of

uncovering hair seems empowering to Kemalist Sunay Zaim but Kadife experiences it as shameful not as empowering. When asked about the role that the headscarf debate plays in this novel during an interview with Alexander Star of the New York Times in 2004, Pamuk explained:

“I try to focus on these issues not from the point of view of a statesman but from the point of view of a person who tries to understand the pain and suffering of others. ... I think literature can approach these problems because you can go into more shady areas, areas where no one is right and no one has the right to say what is right. ... It's what makes writing a political novel interesting”.

Thus the novel *Snow* posits some intricately territorial questions regarding belief and identity. After serving her sentence for killing Sunay (the murder was planned by Sunay himself) Kadife has undergone a transformation from a rebellious political Islamist to a devout Muslim woman who is happily married to Fazil. Thus the identity of a subject position need to be understood not only historically but also spatially as different local political movements have a crucial role to play in their identity formation. Above all politics is territorial and the territories may be real, imaginary or symbolical.

Pamuk's novels, in general, are characterized by a confusion brought on in part by the clashing cultural values between European and Islamic standards. But there is perhaps a final and more profound conclusion to draw from these novels. Pamuk's narrative trickery, surrealistic, elliptical, marginal and carnivalesque renderings of action and recuperation of traditional Sufi themes and Ottoman past, make it clear that binary choices are problematic. Actually his creative consciousness enables a re-evaluation of the understanding of the spectrum between the extremes of the East and the West. Pamuk's novels reflect his incredulity towards grand narratives --an authentic postmodernist approach--- within which he resists monolithic universal ideals and encourages fractured, fluid and multiple perspectives. He repeatedly returns to the concerns of the past heritage rather than a continual linear drive towards newness and such a technique enables him to project the tension between pro-Western modernity and tradition in the context of Islamic culture. Whenever Pamuk has been questioned about the complex ambivalence of Eastern and Western values he answers in relatively calm terms. But his novelistic world presents a different picture where the undercurrent feeling about the relationship appears stormier and troubled. In a very recent book, *Between Cultures: Europe and its Others in Five Exemplary Lives*, Jerrold Seigel commented about the personal root of such ambivalence. In his view it lies “into the evolution of Pamuk's native country and city. Geography has something to do with it, given that Istanbul stands on the both banks of the Bosphorus, Europe on one side and Asian on the other; but the stronger grounds are historical” (197).

In his novels Turkish history and cultural memory and the controversial facets of its national and international geopolitical concerns negotiate each other and bring about a deeper understanding between the East and the West. To only focus on the East- West dialectic would be a kind of injustice to the value of this novel because this novel is a consistent representation of Pamuk's literary engagement with politics and ‘dissident literary modernity’ (Erdag Goknar,183). Like his other novels, *Snow* also focuses on various manifestations of Sufism and Ottoman cultural history. To conclude we can quote

from a short essay for the Council of Europe on the concept of writing frontiers where Pamuk observes:

I have spent my life in Istanbul, on the European shore, in the houses looking towards the Asian shore. Living by the water with a view of the opposite shore ceaselessly reminded me of my place in the world. Then one day a bridge connecting the two shores of the Bosphorous was built. When I went up on the bridge and surveyed the landscape, I realized it was still better and still more lovely to see the two shores at once. I felt that a bridge between two shores was the best thing to be. Speaking to each shore without completely belonging to either; this unveiled the finest scenery of all. (“The Bridge”)

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